

Path Integral Formulation of Free Propagator and Maximum Entropy Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 22, 2021

In a previous note (Part I), we argued that introducing a Fourier transform into the path integral calculation of the free particle propagator (as done in (1)) i.e. bringing in $\exp(ipx)$ represents fluctuations in momentum. The free particle moves from X to Y with a constant average velocity, but p in $\exp(ipx)$ represents physical momentum which may be positive or negative. This motion is inherent in the calculation of the path integral which yields the free particle propagator. An explicit calculation is performed in (1).

In this note, we consider a slightly different calculation of the free particle propagator. We use the classical action, but not path integrals following the approach of (1) for the quantum oscillator. In particular, we calculate $x = X v(T_f - t)/(T_f - T_i) + Y v(t - T_i)/(T_f - T_i)$ and from this obtain the classical Lagrangian which is integrated over time. We see that the math object $Q(t)\exp(i S_c)$ satisfies a math equation which is the time dependent Schrodinger equation:

$$i\partial/\partial t (\text{partial}) Q(t) \exp(i S_c) = -1/2m \partial/\partial x \partial/\partial x Q(t) \exp(i S_c).$$

It appears that by using partial derivatives of X and $T = T_f - T_i$, one changes these independently, i.e. the velocity is constant on average. In general, if velocity is constant, T and X are not independent. Thus, we argue that a differential equation describing partial changes in x and t such that the $i\partial/\partial t$ partial and $-1/2m \partial/\partial x \partial/\partial x$ cancel only represents constant velocity free particle motion on average. One may note that the choice to have the X and T changes cancel is a specific rule which leads to a specific differential equation, namely the Schrodinger equation. We also see that the separable function $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ is also a solution of this differential equation (Schrodinger equation) and incorporates the idea of p and E being constant on average. In particular, the free particle propagator $\exp[-i m/2 (X - Y)(X - Y)/T]$ is $\exp(-iET)$ if one forces kinetic energy to be constant i.e. E . In that case, an extra factor of $\exp(ipx)$ is needed and one sees fluctuations more clearly.

Propagator for a Free Particle

The propagator for a free particle is $Q(t)\exp(i S_c)$ where $Q(t)$ is a fluctuation term and $S_c = \int L_c(t_1) dt_1$, $L_c(t_1)$ being the classical Lagrangian $L_c = T - V$. Here $V = 0$. S_c may be calculated directly using:

$$x(t) = X v(T_f - t) / v(T_f - T_i) + Y v(t - T_i) / v(T_f - T_i) \quad ((1))$$

“ v ”, the velocity, drops out, but there is still an average velocity given by:

$$dx/dt = (-X + Y) / T \quad \text{where } T = T_f - T_i \quad ((2))$$

The Lagrangian is $m/2 (-X + Y)(-X + Y)/(T)$ ((3)) so the action is $m/2 (-X + Y)(-X + Y)/(T)$

Thus, $\exp(iSc)$ is $\exp\{i [m/2 (-X+Y)(-X+Y)/(T)]\}$ ((4))

Derivative Properties of $(X-Y)/T$

$(X-Y)/T$ has the form of an average velocity. $\exp(iSc)$ has the form of a function of X, Y, T . If Y is held fixed and velocity is constant, then X and T are dependent. The idea of the propagator, however, is that one may vary X and T independently, i.e. velocity is not held constant. In particular, one may create a differential equation, such that a term with a change in T is balanced by another term with a change in X leading to an overall result of zero. Given the form $(X-Y)/T$ one may see that T in the denominator increases in negative power with d/dT while X decreases with d/dX . Thus, $d/dT f((X-Y)/T) = -df/dz ((X-Y)/T)$ where $z = (X-Y)/T$. If one had an argument of $(X-Y)(X-Y)/T$ in a complex function $\exp(i g((X-Y)(X-Y)/T))$ then id/dt would create a real term which could match a $-d/dX$ d/dX term. There would be an additional purely imaginary term from d/dX d/dX with no X present so a factor of $Q(t)$ multiplying $\exp(i g((X-Y)(X-Y)/T))$ will satisfy the imaginary equation. $(X-Y)(X-Y)/TT$ (T) has the form of the Lagrangian multiplied by time or the classical action.

In other words, one may take the purely classical object $\exp(i Sc)$ and find that it is the solution of a differential equation:

$$id/dT \exp(i Sc) Q(T) = Q(T) (-1/2m) d/dX d/dX \exp(iSc) \quad ((5))$$

Classically, however, one would not write such an equation because for fixed Y and velocity, X is a function of T , the two are not independent. Thus, it seems that ((5)), even though based on a classical quantity $\int dt L_c(t)$, allows for changes in X and T independently and hence allows for some kind of fluctuations. An immediate question is: Why should the change in T match/cancel the change in X ?

One may argue that one may have fluctuations in T and X within a certain function, but insist that overall these fluctuations or changes yield no average effect. One may argue that the time-dependent Schrodinger equation which follows from this criterion together with the form $\exp(iSc)$ satisfies this requirement. Thus, although Sc is purely classical, changing X and T independently is not. The time dependent Schrodinger equation follows from the choice that these X and T changes in the function cancel. If X and T simply change with no overall rule (dictating the changes), one does not obtain an equation.

$\exp(ipx - iEt)$ Form

It is known that $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ is a solution of equation ((5)) which no $Q(T)$ needed. If one examines the free particle propagator portion $\exp(iSc) = \exp[-i m/2 (X-Y)(X-Y)/T]$ it may be seen that $m/2(X-Y)(X-Y)/(TT)$ is kinetic energy which should be a constant. Then, $\exp(iSc)$ is equivalent to $\exp(-i ET)$. This is not a solution of the Schrodinger equation, but does satisfy the LHS id/dt (partial) yielding $E \exp(iEt)$. Thus, the RHS should behave as $\exp(ipx)$ with p

constant. E and p define averages as the Schrodinger equation is already a nonclassical equation describing some kind of fluctuations. Given that $\exp(ipx)$ is periodic in x already suggests an average constant p with an associated length proportional to $1/p$ over which some kind of fluctuation occurs. This is repeated periodically.

It may be noted that $px-Et$ is a Lorentz invariant. It may also be noted that even though the nonrelativistic form $\frac{1}{2}m(X-Y)(X-Y)/(TT)$ is used, X and T are both treated as dimensions when creating the differential equation which allows for changes (fluctuations) in both with the rule that the function does not change. The Lagrangian has to be integrated over t to allow for a proper form.

Statistical Considerations

We argue that statistical considerations are included in this process. As has been seen, $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ are solutions of the resulting differential equation (Schrodinger equation). Both have moduli of 1 suggesting a $P(t)=\text{constant}$ i.e. regular motion in time and $P(x)=\text{constant}$ i.e. no preference in space. This seems to match a free quantum particle. The statistical features seem to enter by using the form $\exp(iSc)$ which has a modulus of 1. In other words, one develops an equation of fluctuations, but the overall behaviour (i.e. modulus) represents the usual classical physics for the free particle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the form $\exp(iSc)$, where Sc is the classical action for a free propagator with $x(t)=X(T_f-t)/T + Y(t-T_i)/T$ and $T=T_f-T_i$ treats X and T as dimensions and allows for fluctuations subject to the rule that a "special function" namely $\exp(iSc)$ does not change overall when X and T change. This special function seems to have statistical features as its modulus is 1.

The differential equation describing this type of fluctuation turns out to be the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. If one wishes to impose constant velocity, then $\exp(iSc)=\exp(-iEt)$, but an $\exp(ipx)$ factor is needed to satisfy the Schrodinger equation i.e. there needs to be an x portion. The solution is then separable, with each piece describing a fluctuation in the respective dimension.

References

1.https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Path_integral_formulation#Free_particle